

PHYTOCHEMICAL SCREENING OF SAPWOOD OF VALUABLE MEDICINAL TREE OF FOREST- *Pterocarpus marsupium*

(Roxb.)

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Abstract

Pterocarpus marsupium has known traditional and ethnobotanical uses since past thousands of years. The present study was carried out to screen the sapwood samples for different phytochemicals using different solvents. Sapwood samples were collected from forest division of Gondiya district and processed. The powdered samples were subjected to extraction with three solvents of increasing polarity i.e. methanol, petroleum ether and chloroform. These extracts were evaluated for phytochemicals qualitatively as well as quantitatively. Results indicated the extraction of phytochemicals better in polar solvents i.e. distilled methanol and chloroform. Moreover, the extracts of these solvents were found to contain tannins, phenols, saponins, flavonoids, terpenoids, alkaloids of pharmacological importance. Quantitative estimation of the tannin (%), phenol (%) antioxidant activity ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) and ascorbic acid ($\text{mg}/100\text{ml}$) revealed range of variation. This indicates influence of genotype, environment and GxE interaction on the phytochemicals

.Keywords: *Pterocarpus marsupium*, stem bark, phytochemicals, qualitative and quantitative screening

Introduction

Since ancient times, various herbs, shrubs, climbers, trees are being used in treatments of various ailments. As per the reports of the World Health Organization (WHO), medicinal plants are being used two to three times more than conventional drugs as remedial measures in curing various ailments (Evans, 1994). *Pterocarpus marsupium* (Roxb.) is one of such valuable medicinal trees of tropical forest having multifarious medicinal uses. Its medicinal significance has been reported in Indian traditional systems of medicine like Ayurveda, Unani and Homeopathy (Badkhane et al. 2000). *Pterocarpus marsupium*, commonly known as Bijasalor Vijaysar (in Hindi), Asana (in Sanskrit), Malabar Kino or Indian Kino (in English) and by many other names, is a deciduous tree of fabaceae family. It is multipurpose leguminous tree having yellow flowers. It's flowering and fruiting period is March to June (Yadav and Sardesai, 2002). Fruit is circular, flat, winged pod. Seed is convex and bony (Warrier, 1995). The tree is indigenous to India, Nepal and Sri Lanka (Gamble, 1935; Matthew, 1983). It is distributed in deciduous forest of the country (Varghese, 1996) and reported in the forests of Madhya Pradesh, Chhattisgarh, Maharashtra, Andhra Pradesh, Bihar, Karnataka, Kerala, Orissa, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal (Sanjappa, 2000). It attains height up to 15-20 meter and has dark brown to grey bark having swallow cracks. The bark exudes a red gummy substance called 'Gum Kino' when injured (Patil and Gaikwad, 2011). Almost each and every plant part of the *Pterocarpus marsupium* is reported to have uses in curing various diseases. It has long history of numerous ethno medicinal uses. Leaves are used for curing the boils, sores, skin diseases and stomach pain; flowers in fever; Gum Kino for diarrhea, dysentery, leucorrhoea etc. (Anonymous, 2001; Pullaiah, 1999). The heartwood of *Pterocarpus marsupium* is known to possess astringent, anti-inflammatory, anti-diabetic and anodyne properties (Kirtikar, 1987). The heartwood is an important source of Pterostilbene (Mathew et al. 1977; Dama et al. 1982) which has numerous clinical applications (Estrela et al. 2013; McCormack and McFadden 2013). Decoction of bark and resin is used for the treatment of tumors of the gland, urethral discharges and as abortifacient (Basu, 1975). Due to unsustainable extraction coupled with low natural regeneration and population fragmentation, *Pterocarpus marsupium* is now listed as 'Vulnerable' in the IUCN red data list (IUCN, 2017)

Present study was undertaken with aim to screen the sapwood samples of *Pterocarpus marsupium* collected from Gondiya district of Maharashtra for major phytochemicals and also to assess the variations for selected phytochemicals i.e. the tannin, phenol, antioxidant activity and ascorbic acid.

Material and Methods**Collection of material and processing**

sapwood samples were collected from two different villages in Gondiya district of Maharashtra (Table 1). Number of trees sampled were 25 varied from indicated in Table 1. The sapwood samples was dried in hot air at 105°C. Dried sapwood samples were ground into fine powder using grinder machine.

Qualitative phytochemical analysis

200 mg of powdered sapwood material of each tree was kept overnight in 5 ml of different solvents viz. methanol, petroleum ether and chloroform. Filtered extracts were subjected to preliminary phytochemical testing for different phytochemicals by standard methods as described by Harborne (1973).

Test for Tannins**Ferric chloride test**

Presence of tannins in various plant extracts was determined with the protocol reported by Sofowara (1993). 50 mg of crude extract was boiled in 20 ml of water in test tubes then filtered. Addition of few drops of 0.1% ferric chloride was mixed and observed for colour change, the presence of brownish green colour or blue-black coloration indicated presence of tannins (Harborne and Williams, 1998).

Test for Phenols**Gelatin test (Evans, 1997)**

The extract (50 mg) was dissolved in 5ml of distilled water and 2ml of 1% solution of gelatin containing 10% sodium chloride was added to it. White precipitate indicated the presence of phenols.

Test for Saponins**Foaming test**

Determination of saponins in various plant extracts was carried out according to Harborne (1973). The extracts were diluted with distilled water and volume was made up to 20 ml. The suspension was shaken in a graduated cylinder for 15 min. The layer of foam indicated the presence of saponins (Kokate, 1999).

Test for flavonoids**Shinoda test**

Presence of flavonoids in various plant extracts was determined with the protocol reported by Mace (1963). In this method an aqueous solution of the extracts was treated with 10% ammonium hydroxide solution. Yellow fluorescence indicated the presence of flavonoids.

Test for Terpenoids**Salkowski test**

Presence of terpenoids in various plant extracts was determined according to Harborne (1973). 5 ml (1mg/ml) of the extract was mixed with 2 ml of chloroform and then 3 ml of concentrated H₂SO₄. Change of reddish-brown coloration of the interface showed the presence of the terpenoids.

Test for alkaloids

Dragendorff's test

By adding 1 ml of Dragendorff's reagent to 2 ml of extract, an orange red precipitate was formed, indicating the presence of alkaloids

Quantitative phytochemical analysis

Estimation of Tannin : Tannin were estimated by Folin-Denis Method (Thimmaiah,1999). 200 mg of the powdered material was boiled (30 minutes) with 50 ml of distilled water in a 250 ml flask. The contents were then centrifuged for 20 minutes and the supernatant was made to 100 ml with distilled water. 1 ml of the above sample extract was then taken in a 100 ml volumetric flask containing 75 ml distilled water and to it 5 ml of Folin-Denis reagent and 10 ml of sodium carbonate solution were added. The total volume was then made to 100 ml with distilled water. After shaking and allowing it to stand for 30 minutes, absorbance was recorded at 700 nm. Standard graph was prepared by taking 0, 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 ml of working standard solution of tannic acid and using the other reagents as mentioned above. Blank was

prepared by taking distilled water. Tannins content was calculated as tannic acid equivalent from standard graph.

Estimation of Phenol: The total phenolic content of the extracts was determined by using Folin Ciocalteu reagent. 100mg of the extract of the sample was weighed and dissolved in 100 ml of t distilled water. 1 ml of this solution was transferred to a test tube, then 0.5 ml 2N of the Folin-Ciocalteu reagent and 1.5 ml 20% of Na₂CO₃ solution was added. Final volume was made up to 8 ml with distilled water followed by vigorous shaking and finally allowed to stand for 2 hours after which the absorbance was taken at 765 nm. These data were used to estimate the total phenolic content using a standard calibration curve obtained from various diluted concentrations of gallic acid.

Estimation of Antioxidant activity: DPPH scavenging activity tests were carried out according to the method of Brand Williams *et al.*, 1995 for which 100 mg of the sample was dissolved in 10 ml ethanol and concentration (10mg/ml) was prepared. 2 ml DPPH solution was added into 10 µl of the sample solutions. The mixture was shake vigorously and incubated 30 minute in 30°C water bath. Absorbance of the resulting solution was measured at 517 nm UV visible spectrophotometer. All the assays were carried out in the triplicates with ethanol as a control and Gallic acid which was used as the standard antioxidant.

Percentage of inhibition (DPPH scavenging activity) determined as follows.

$$\% \text{DPPH radical - scavenging} = \frac{(\text{Absorbance of DPPH} - \text{Absorbance of sample})}{\text{Absorbance of DPPH}}$$

(Burcin *et al.*, 2010)

Estimation of Ascorbic acid : The ascorbic acid content was estimated by using the method described by Rangana (2001). A known volume of sample was taken and transferred to 100 ml volumetric flasks and volume was made up with 3 per cent metaphosphoric acid. From this, 10 ml aliquot was taken into 100 ml beaker and titrated against 2,6-dichlorophenol-indophenol dye solution until the faint pink colour was appeared. The result was expressed as mg of ascorbic acid 100 ml⁻¹ edible portion. Standardization of dye: Standarization of 2,6-dichlorophenol-indophenols dye was done by titrating it against standard ascorbic acid solution. The standard was prepared by dissolving 100 mg of pure L-ascorbic acid in 100 ml of 3 per cent metaphosphoric acid. Then 1 ml of ascorbic acid solution (aliquot) was used for titration

Results and Discussion

Qualitative analysis of extracts of bark of *Pterocarpus marsupium* revealed the presence of tannins, phenols, saponins, flavonoids, terpenoids and alkaloids mostly in polar solvents (methanol and chloroform). Earlier, Ramya *et al.* and Patil & Gaikwad (2011) also reported the presence of alkaloids, glycosides, flavonoids, terpenoids and alkaloids in the stem bark of this species. Contrary to the present findings, they did not find the saponins in bark samples screened. Three

solvents of different polarity were used for extraction of the sapwood sample (Table 2). It is cleared that methanol and chloroform are better solvents for extraction of the major phytochemicals. Specifically, qualitative tests of tannin, flavonoids, terpenoids and phenol were better with these two polar solvents compared to petroleum ether. The qualitative results were better in methanol for tannins, flavonoids, terpenoids and alkaloids while tannins, phenol, flavonoids and terpenoids were also found better with chloroform. Quantitative estimation of the tannin, phenol, antioxidant activity and ascorbic acid was carried out and estimates were presented in Table 3. Critical perusal of the Table 3 revealed that variation in range of phytochemicals. This suggests that environmental, genotypic and their interactions may have profound effect on the phytochemical content. Considering the overall findings of the present study, it is apparent that *Pterocarpus marsupium* possesses major phytochemicals in its sapwood and these phytochemicals may be contributing for the medicinal properties of the sapwood of this species.. This may be due to the genotypic and/or environmental effect and their interaction. This also revealed the scope for selection of promising trees having higher amount of phytochemical contents.

Table 1: Details of the sampling of *Pterocarpus marsupium* in Gondiya District

Sr. No.	Name of Geolocation	Name of District	Name of Forest Division	No. of trees sampled
1.	Bodunda, Timezari	Gondiya	Gondiya	25

Table 2: Qualitative analysis of phytochemical in sapwood samples of *Pterocarpus marsupium* collected from forest division of Gondiya District

Tests	Appearance	Methanol	Petroleum Ether	Chloroform
Tannins	Blue-black	+++	-	+++
Phenols	White	++	-	+++
Saponins	Foam layer	++	-	++
Flavonoids	Yellow	+++	+++	+++
Terpenoids	Reddish-brown	+++	+++	+++
Alkaloids	Orange-red	+++	-	++

Where, '+++': Present in high concentration, '++': Present in moderate concentration, '-': Absent

Table 3: Estimates of tannin, phenol, antioxidant activity and ascorbic acid in sapwood samples of *Pterocarpus marsupium* collected Gondiya District

Phytochemical	Range	Average	Standard Error
Tannin (%)	06.88-12.89	9.35	0.365
Phenol (%)	08.34-12.89	10.25	0.273
Antioxidant Activity(µg/ml)	24.04-38.00	32.12	0.979
Ascorbic Acid (mg/100 ml)	170-210	187.44	1.700

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